

Synthesis of some salts of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine chelates of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)

Shashi K. Gupta, Rashmi Sharma and R. S. Sindhu*

Regional Institute of Education, Bhopal-462 013, India

Manuscript received 21 February 2000, revised 8 June 2000, accepted 30 November 2000

A series of $[(Cp)_2TiL]^+X^-$ compound, where $X^- = I^-, Br^-, ClO_4^-, ZnCl_3^-, CdCl_4^{2-}, HgCl_3^-$ and $FeCl_4^-$ and HL = 2,3-dihydroxypyridine and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine, have been synthesized. The studies demonstrate tetrahedral coordination around the titanium atom.

It has been reported¹ that Cp_2TiCl_2 forms chelates with uninegative bidentate ligands in ionic form as $[(Cp)_2TiL]^+Cl^-$, where L is the conjugate base of the bidentate ligand. To extend the studies in this field we tried the reaction of uninegative bidentate ligands 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP)² and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP)³ with Cp_2TiCl_2 in aqueous medium. The complex species so formed were further treated with KI, KBr, $NaClO_4$, $ZnCl_2$, $CdCl_2$, $HgCl_2$ and $FeCl_3$ salts resulting in the formation of insoluble salts.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes of DHP and AHP have been assigned the compositions $[(Cp)_2TiL]^+X^-$, where HL = DHP/AHP and $X^- = I^-, Br^-, ClO_4^-, ZnCl_3^-, CdCl_4^{2-}, HgCl_3^-$ or $FeCl_4^-$, which have been further confirmed by conductance values ($27.2-30.2 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) for all complexes except for $[(Cp)_2TiL]_2^+CdCl_4^{2-}$ ($54.3 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$). The complexes are thermally stable and decomposed at higher temperature without melting. They are moderately soluble in nitrobenzene, methanol and deuterated acetone.

IR spectra of the compounds showed usual peaks for $\eta^5-C_5H_5$ group⁴, viz. C-H stretching frequency at $\sim 3085 cm^{-1}$, C-C asymmetric ring breathing mode of π -bond at $\sim 1430 cm^{-1}$, C-H in-plane bending vibrations at $\sim 1035 cm^{-1}$ and C-H bending out-of-plane deformation band at $\sim 815 cm^{-1}$. Further an additional band near $440 cm^{-1}$ can be assigned to Ti-C₅H₅ vibration⁵.

The free DHP ligand displayed a broad band at $3200 cm^{-1}$ (O-H---O)⁶ which disappeared in all metal complexes showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of M-O bond at 3-position. The strong ligand band at $1625 cm^{-1}$ (C=O) shifted to lower side in the complexes, suggesting that ligand coordinates to metal through oxygen of carbonyl group at its 2-position. Metal-to-oxygen bonding is further confirmed due to the presence of a band at $490-540 cm^{-1}$ (Ti-O)⁷.

The free AHP ligand displayed three bands at 3425 (O-H---N), 3375 (N-H asym) and $3125 cm^{-1}$ (N-H sym). Stretching O-H band of the ligand disappeared in all the complexes showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of M-O bond to take place at 3-position of the ligand. The N-H sym band at $3125 cm^{-1}$ shifted to lower side by $30-40 cm^{-1}$ indicating that nitrogen of amino group at 2-position is coordinated to metal atom in all AHP complexes. The band at $470-500 cm^{-1}$ (Ti-N) further confirms the presence of a Ti-N bond⁸.

No halide bridging was observed in the complexes of DHP and AHP and the frequencies observed at $360-390 cm^{-1}$ region for complex haloanion salts are characteristics of complex haloanions⁹.

PMR spectral data of the DHP and AHP complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The resonance signal due to C₅H₅ occurs at 6.60 ppm. The existence of single sharp C₅H₅ resonance is attributed to rapid rotation of ring about metal ring axis¹⁰. In case of the complexes the chemical shifts of protons of chelated DHP and AHP indicate that there is bonding of titanium through oxygen atoms at 2- and 3-positions of DHP and nitrogen and oxygen at 2- and 3-positions of AHP. The integrated proton ratios correspond to the formulae assigned to these compounds.

Table 1. Chemical shifts (δ) of complexes (HL = DHP)

Compd.	C ₅ H ₅	Protons of complexed DHP			
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+I^-$	6.62	1.70	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+Br^-$	6.60	1.72	1.80	2.60	1.86
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ClO_4^-$	6.62	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+ZnCl_3^-$	6.62	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.86
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+CdCl_4^{2-}$	6.56	1.76	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+HgCl_3^-$	6.62	1.72	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2TiL]^+FeCl_4^-$	6.62	1.70	1.80	2.60	1.82

Table 2. Chemical shifts (δ) of complexes (HL = AHP)

Compd.	C ₅ H ₅	Protons of complexed AHP pyridine ring			Amino protons
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ I ⁻	6.62	3.4	1.80	2.74	7.32
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ Br ⁻	6.62	3.4	1.80	2.74	7.30
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ ClO ₄ ⁻	6.62	3.2	1.80	2.74	7.30
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ ZnCl ₃	6.64	3.4	1.82	2.70	7.30
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ CdCl ₄ ²⁻	6.58	3.2	1.82	2.72	7.32
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ HgCl ₃	6.62	3.4	1.82	2.70	7.30
[(Cp) ₂ TiL] ⁺ FeCl ₄ ⁻	6.60	3.2	1.80	2.72	7.30

From these studies it can be concluded that the ligand DHP or AHP is chelating with Ti^{IV} and Cp₂Ti₂²⁺ moiety possesses wedge-like sandwich structure with tetrahedral coordination about the metal atom similar to that of dichloride¹¹ and halides and complexohalogeno anions form salts with the [(Cp)₂TiL]⁺ complex cationic species.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Cp₂TiCl₂ (Fluka) and DHP and AHP (Aldrich) were used.

Microanalysis of C and H were carried out in Microanalytical Laboratory of Delhi University. N and halogens were estimated by standard methods¹².

Conductance was measured in nitrobenzene with a Toshniwal conductometer at room temperature. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra ((CD₃)₂CO) at a sweep width of 60 MHz and a sweep time of 300 s on a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer R-600 FTNMR spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Preparation of the compounds : To an aqueous solution of Cp₂TiCl₂ (5 mmol) in water (50 ml), solid DHP/AHP (5 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2 h. It was then added dropwise with shaking to a concentrated hot aqueous solution containing excess (6 mmol) of KI, KBr, NaClO₄, ZnCl₂, CdCl₂, HgCl₂ and FeCl₃, until no more precipitate was formed. The precipitate so obtained was digested over water bath at 60–70° for 2 h, washed with hot water and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

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